

THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESSES IN SHORT FIBRE ALUMINA REINFORCED AL-ALLOY MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method for determining the thermal residual stress distribution in an alumina reinforced aluminium-alloy. The residual stresses have great influence on the toughness and strength behaviour of the composite. The machinability is also dependent on both the fibre volume fraction and the residual stresses.

Several methods for determining the thermal residual stresses in different kinds of composites have been presented. By using the finite element method (FEM) to investigate "cells", the composite stresses can be calculated. Different geometries of the fibre ends and fibre volume fractions (up to 30%) have been used. The interfacial properties of the composite, e.g. the degree of bonding has a great influence on the stress distribution.

The composite has an initial temperature of 577°C and has then been cooled to room temperature. The matrix has plastic material properties with both strain hardening and yielding that are temperature dependent. The influence of the fibre volume fraction, material properties and degree of bonding on the stress distribution is discussed.

Keywords: matrix, aluminum, fibre, ceramic, short fibre composite, residual stress, finite element analysis.

1 BACKGROUND

As a result of increasing demands on the performance of construction materials, metal matrix composites (MMC) have gained in importance. By making use of the the specific advantages of the constituents in the composite such as the low density and the high strength of the fibres, the material properties of the composites can be optimized for the applications. The complex material properties however necessitate the analysis and modelling of the material behaviour of the composite. Processing and manufacturing properties such as machinability however also have to be studied.

Due to the different material properties of the matrix and the fibre regarding Young's modulus E , the coefficient of thermal expansion α and Poisson's ratio ν , residual stresses appear in the composite during cooling after casting. The residual stresses depend on the geometry of the casting and the anisotropy of the composite. Other parameters with influence on the residual

stresses are the fibre volume fraction (V_f), the bonding strength between fibre and matrix and the geometrical shape of the fibre ends.

The residual stresses of the composite can give a qualitative idea of the toughness behaviour and machinability of the composite. FEM-calculations of composite cells is one possible method of modelling the stress distribution in composites. This has been done by McMeeking[1], Needleman[2], Karlsson[3] and Stuesson et al[4].

In general, internal stresses have a strong influence on the possibilities of cold working and machining. For example the machinability of cold rolled tube blanks depend strongly on the residual stress condition[5]. The cutting forces decrease at the same time as the tool life increases during machining of materials where axial tensile stresses are obtained in production. In metal matrix composites, other effects such as improved chip breaking and lower tendency of built-up edge formation also influence the decreased cutting forces[6].

2 MODELLING

2.1 Geometries

Figure 1. a) Model for no bonding. b) Model for full bonding. c) Model for axisymmetry analysis.

Three different types of models have been used in this study. The two extreme cases no bonding/full bonding between fiber and matrix and one model to study the influence of the fibre end geometry on the stress distribution.

For the simulation of no bonding between fibre and matrix the two-dimensional model shown in figure 1.a have been used. The model is based upon a geometry of nine fibres. The centre of the model has been analysed and its symmetry has been made use of. The model consist of 8-node two-dimensional elements.

For the simulation of full bonding between fibre and matrix a three-dimensional model shown in figure 1.b have been used. In order to minimize times of analysis one more case of symmetry can be made use of, $y=x$. Geometrically, these models correspond to half of the two-dimensional ones and they are swept in z-direction to obtain depth. The model consist of 15-node and 20-node solid elements.

In order to study how different fibre end geometries affect the stress field around the fibre end, axially symmetrical models as in figure 1.c have been made. These axially symmetrical models are made up of a cross-section of a fibre end in a matrix. In the model, 8- and 6-node elements have been used.

2.2 Material properties

The composite has a matrix consisting of Al-Mg-Si1 and fibres of alumina (SAFFIL). The fibre is presumed to have completely ideal-elastic, temperature independent material properties, see table 1. The matrix (Al-Mg-Si1) is presumed to have elastic-plastic material properties with

E_f (N/mm ²)	ν_f	α_f (1/°C)
$3.1 \cdot 10^5$	0.22	$8.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Table 1. The material data of the fibre (SAFFIL)[16].

temperature dependent coefficient of thermal expansion, Young's modulus, yield stress and strain hardening, see figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curves of the matrix (Al-Mg-Si1) at $T = 20, 100, 180, 240, 300$ and 400 °C [17][18][19].

2.3 Loading

The composite is cooled from a stress-free condition at 577°C to 20°C (room temperature).

2.4 Boundary conditions

Residual stresses are calculated theoretically in two extreme cases:

- Full bonding between fibre and matrix.
- No bonding between fibre and matrix.

In the latter case, which corresponds to a plane stress condition, no shearing stresses will be transferred along the fibre. However, a compression of fibres occurs if the coefficient of thermal expansion of the matrix is greater than that of the fibre. In the other extreme, the same deformation occurs in the boundary layer between fibre and matrix.

2.5 Simplifications and delimitations

The following idealizations have been made:

- Totally isotropic material properties in both fibre and matrix.

Figure 3. a) The thermal expansion coefficient and b) Young's modulus, of the matrix (Al-Mg-Si1) as a function of temperature[17][19].

- Full and no bonding have been studied.
- The Young's modulus of the fibre is independent of temperature.
- Ideal distribution of fibres in the composite.
- No phase transformations take place in the composite.
- Cooling is uniform throughout the composite cell, i.e. infinite cell.
- The matrix is not relaxed during cooling.

3 RESULTS

The results of the analysis are taken into account in the form of isostress plots from different calculation models and diagrams where normal stresses, shearing stresses and von Mises effective stress are plotted as a function of the relative distance from the fibre centre. Moreover, stresses as a function of the fibre volume fraction and of the fibre geometry, are accounted for.

Figure 4. Major principal stress, σ_1 at 20% fibres, a) no bonding and b) full bonding.

Figure 5. Effective stress, σ_e^M at 20% fibres, a) sharp fibre end, b) cone-shaped fibre end.

Figure 6. a) Effective stress, σ_e^M at 20% fibres with ball-shaped end, b) Major principal stress as a function of fibre volume fraction and geometry of the fibre end.

Figure 7. Radial stress, σ_r at a) no bonding and b) full bonding as a function of the relative distance from the fibre center and fibre volume fraction.

Figure 8. Tangential stress, σ_θ at a) no bonding and b) full bonding as a function of the relative distance from the fibre center and fibre volume fraction.

Figure 9. Axial stress, σ_z at full bonding as a function of the relative distance from the fibre center and fibre volume fraction.

Figure 10. Effective stress, σ_e^M at a) no bonding and b) full bonding as a function of the relative distance from the fibre center and fibre volume fraction.

3.1 Results summary

No bonding

Radial stresses, σ_r

- The fibre is the subject of compressive radial stresses. The reason to this is that the fibre is squeezed by the matrix due to different thermal expansion coefficients. Lower fibre volume fraction gives higher compressive radial stresses.
- In the matrix decreases the radial compressive stress and levels out at -40 MPa independent of the fibre volume fraction.

Tangential stresses, σ_θ

- The fibre is the subject of compressive tangential stresses. In the fibre/matrix interface the tangential stresses change to high tensile ones and reaches maximum value in the matrix at some distance from the interface. This is due to the fact that the matrix is pressed against a circular fibre and is squeezed out tangential to the fibre. Further out in the matrix the tensile tangential stresses decreases.
- At higher fibre volume fraction does not the tangential stresses decrease but are constant high between the fibres.

Effective stresses, σ_e^M

- In the fibre the effective stress is approximately constant. At lower fibre volume fraction effective stresses are higher.
- In the matrix the effective stress increases to a maximum value at 310 MPa regardless of the fibre volume fraction. Further out in the matrix the effective stress then decreases. At higher fibre volume fraction the effective stress remains high in the matrix.

Full bonding

Radial stresses, σ_r

- There are high compressive radial stresses in the fibre, the compressive stresses decrease with increasing fibre volume fraction.
- In the matrix the radial stresses increases and levels out at -40 MPa regardless of the fibre volume fractions.

Tangential stresses, σ_θ

- The fibre has high compressive tangential stresses.
- In the matrix the stresses increases to a maximum value outside the fibre and then the stresses decreases further away from the fibre. At large fibre volume fractions the stresses remain high in the matrix.
- The difference between different fibre volume fractions is small.

Axial stresses, σ_z

- The axial compressive stresses are high in the fibre. In the matrix the stresses increase to positive values and is then constant out in the matrix at 100 – 150 MPa.
- There are no large differences in the axial stress between different fibre volume fractions.

Effective stresses, σ_e^M

- In the fibre the effective stresses are high.
- In the matrix near the interface the stresses are very high, around 310 MPa. Further out in the matrix the stresses decrease. There are almost no difference in effective stresses with different fibre volume fractions in the matrix.

Different fibre end shape

With cone-shaped fibre end, the tensile stresses in the matrix are lowest. The tensile stresses increase with increasing fibre volume fraction. The effective stresses are also lowest with the cone-shaped fibre end. To get better knowledge about the influence of fibre end shape the calculations must be carried out with more than one fibre.

4 DISCUSSION

In the present model, no stress relaxation, physical or chemical transformations of the matrix material during the cooling process are taken into account. Thus, this analysis gives a mapping of the local elastic energy input but only upper bounds for the limiting cases of residual stress build up.

Creep and stress relaxation, strain hardening and the behaviour and properties obtained by hot working of this kind of composites and matrix materials however have been the subject of extensive studies elsewhere [8][12][14][15]. The effects of these features are far from negligible. The final properties are thus strongly dependent on the subsequent thermomechanical history of the material.

A strain hardened zone around alumina or SiC fibres exhibiting reduced plasticity created by the thermal expansion mismatch in a light alloy matrix can be expected to have importance for the improved machining properties with cutting forces decreasing with increasing fibre content, as reported by Andersson et al[6]. The same mechanism however can also be expected to give the not very good impact properties obtained for this kind of materials[10].

The tensile stress gradients from the fibre/matrix interface into the matrix provide free energy and thus driving force for diffusion. The reported segregation of second phase into the fibre matrix interface and degradation of the age hardening characteristics of the 6061-type alloys can be thus be explained[9].

Effect of cooling rate on stress relaxation will be a subject of coming modelling work.

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